

DEVELOPMENT OF AN IMPROVED NCAM WET LEGUME DEHULLER

Olotu, F. B., Ademiluyi. Y. S., Okoro, O. N., Obiakor S. C., Jimoh, R. O and Alade, R.
Processing and Storage Engineering Department
National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization, (NCAM), Idofian,
PMB 1525, Ilorin, Kwara State.

ABSTRACT

The traditional method of dehulling legumes such as cowpea, soya beans and locust beans is by rubbing the seeds between the palms or by pounding in mortar but this process consumes time and energy and in some cases unhygienic. An improved wet legume dehuller was designed and fabricated to de-hull wet legumes. It was designed to work on the principle of compression for the splitting of the soaked seed coat. The de-hulling is achieved by shear and friction between the beans coat and the wall of the de-hulling chamber. This machine was designed and fabricated using locally available materials and technology. The Improved Wet Legume dehuller used for dehulling of wet legume seeds like locust bean, cowpea and soybean was fabricated at National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization, (NCAM), Ilorin with the aim of reducing the drudgery encountered by agro processors while dehulling different leguminous seeds to the barest minimum which will impact positively on their ability to process and utilize these legumes. The legume seeds were conditioned based on their required conditions for dehulling: locust bean samples weighing 10kg each were cooked for 9 hours; cowpea samples weighing 5 kg each were soaked for 10 minutes, and soybean samples weighing 5kg each and soaked for 12 hours respectively. These legume seeds were weighed in three replicates and then dehulled at an operating speed of 250 rpm. The highest mean values of dehulling efficiency 74.01%, 89.38% and 86.01% were obtained for cowpea, locust bean and soybean respectively.

KEYWORDS: legume, dehulling, compression, drudgery

1. INTRODUCTION

Legume seeds are important sources of energy and protein in many parts of the world, both in animal and human nutrition (Kaushik *et al.*, 2010). Many legume seeds are relatively small in size but possess a hard outer skin (testa) which is removed by a processing operation known as dehulling. Dehulled cowpea is required in the preparation of some table meals such as fried beans cake-(akara) and boiled cake- (moi moi). Despite the widespread use of common legumes such as cowpea, locust beans and soybeans as food among Nigerians, the dehulling of these legumes is still carried out manually.

Dehulling is the removal of the testa from a seed after the seed has been conditioned, and

it is a critical operation in the processing of legume seeds for human consumption. Traditionally, dehulling of legumes commonly consumed in Nigeria such as cowpea, locust bean and soybean is achieved manually by rubbing the seeds between the palms, stamping the feet on them(as in the case of locust bean) or by pounding in mortar. This method of dehulling is time consuming, labor intensive, unhealthy and unhygienic.

Various legume seeds dehullers have been developed: Olaoye and Olotu (2017) developed a hydro – separating cowpea dehuller; Ndukwu and Onyenwoke (2014) designed and developed a continuous maize dehulling, cleaning and milling machine; Ogunsola *et al.* (2015) developed a motorized

wet soybean dehulling machine and Okunola *et al*, (2019) developed a locust bean dehulling cum washing machine, Egbe and Roland (2016) designed, fabricated and tested a wet legume dehulling machine. These dehullers were developed in a bid to reduce the drudgery associated with the traditional method of dehulling of leguminous seeds.

The dehullers developed so far by researchers were seed-specific, thus limiting their performance when used in the dehulling of other leguminous seeds. The need to develop a machine capable of dehulling a wide range of leguminous seeds is the major driver of this research activity. The objective of this research therefore was to design, fabricate and evaluate the performance of a wet legume dehuller with separator which will be used for dehulling a variety of leguminous seeds.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Design consideration of the Improved Wet-Legume Dehuller

The overall cost of the wet legume dehuller, corrosion resistant properties of selected materials, and availability of selected materials locally were the major factors considered in the design of this machine. Due to corrosion resistant properties, galvanized iron sheet was used for the construction of the auger, inlet and discharge hoppers. Workability and price influenced the choice of plain carbon steel for the shaft. The choice of 50 x 50 mm mild steel angle iron for the frame was influenced by its availability and suitability. The dehulling chamber was constructed using galvanized steel pipe because of its ability to resist corrosion, thereby preventing food contamination.

2.2 Description of the Improved Wet-Legume Dehuller

Major parts of the machine include the Hopper, the dehulling chamber (where dehulling is carried out), the dehulling unit which executes the dehulling operation, discharge outlets for dehulled seeds and chaff (removed hull), the frame which hold the machine components and a 2hp electric motor that generate power for the dehulling operation.

2.3 Operation of the Improved Wet-Legume Dehuller

Conditioned legume seeds (locust beans, cowpea and soybean) are fed into the machine through the inlet hopper. Power required for driving the dehulling operation is generated by a 2hp electric motor and transmitted to the dehulling chamber with the aid of a belt and pulley arrangement. The hull of the legumes are removed from the seeds by the force of abrasion. As soon as dehulling of the legumes is carried out, introduction of water into the dehulling chamber causes the hull to flow through the perforations at the base of the dehulling chamber and onto the chaff collector, while the cleaned seeds are conveyed to the seed discharge hopper.

2.4.1 Design Calculations of the Improved Wet-Legume Dehuller

2.4.1 Hopper Design

The design of the hopper is based on the determination of the volume of frustum of a square based pyramid as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Hopper design (Adejuyigbe and Bolaji, 2005)

Volume of the big pyramid of base ABCD and Vertex I =

$$\frac{1}{3} c^2 (h + y) \quad (1)$$

Volume of the small pyramid of base EFGH and vertex I =

$$\frac{1}{3} k^2 y \quad (2)$$

Volume of Frustrum =

$$\frac{1}{3} [c^2 (h + y) - k^2 y] \quad (3)$$

Height of the small pyramid (y) =

$$\frac{hk}{c-k} \quad (4)$$

Where:

h = height of the frustrum

y = height of the small pyramid

Where:

h = height of the frustrum

y = height of the small pyramid

c = length of one side of the big square based pyramid (ABCD and Vertex I)

k = length of one side of the small square based pyramid (EFGH and Vertex I)

c = 0.41m, h = 0.38m k = 0.15m

Using equation (4), y is calculated as 0.22m Using equation (3), volume of the frustrum, which is the volumetric capacity of the hopper was calculated to be, 0.03197m³

2.4.2 Dehulling Chamber Design

The following values were determined while designing the dehulling chamber:

I. Volume of the Dehulling Chamber

$$V_{dc} = \pi r_{dc}^2 l_{dc} \quad (5)$$

Where:

V_{dc} = Volume of Dehulling chamber

r_{dc} = radius of dehulling chamber (0.06m)

l_{dc} = length of dehulling chamber (0.56m)

$$V_{dc} = 3.142 \times (0.06)^2 \times 0.56 = 0.00633 \text{ m}^3$$

II. Volume of Roller in the Dehulling Chamber

$$V_r = \pi r_r^2 l_r \quad (6)$$

Where,

V_r = Volume of roller

r_r = radius of roller (0.03 m)

l_r = length of roller (0.53 m)

$$V_r = 3.142 \times (0.03)^2 \times 0.53 = 0.00150 \text{ m}^3$$

III. Volume of material in the Dehulling Chamber

$$V_m = V_{dc} - V_r \quad (7)$$

Where,

V_m = Volume of material in the dehulling chamber

V_{dc} = Volume of the dehulling chamber

V_r = Volume of roller

$$V_m = 0.00633 - 0.00150 = 0.00483 \text{ m}^3$$

2.4.3 Determination of Pulley Diameter

The electric motor supplied for during the construction of the improved wet legume dehuller was a 2hp electric motor with a pulley of 50mm diameter and a rotating speed of 1800 rpm. According to Reichert et al. (1979), dehulling of seeds at low speed was more efficient than at high speed therefore the need to design for speed reduction. A machine speed of 320 rpm was designed for. The diameter of the machine pulley was calculated using the equation for the peripheral speed of belt as shown in equation 5 given by (Khurmi and Gupta, 2005) as:

$$N_1 D_1 = N_2 D_2 \quad (8)$$

Where,

- N_1 = Speed of the driving motor in rev/min,
 - N_2 = Speed of the shaft in rev/min
 - D_1 = Diameter of driving pulley in m,
 - D_2 = Diameter of driven pulley in m.
- When $N_1 = 1800$ rpm $D_1 = 50$ mm $N_2 = 320$ rpm

The pulley diameter of the dehuller was calculated to be 280 mm

2.4.4 Determination of Shaft Torque

The torque transmitted by the screw conveyor shafts was 0.0069 Nm calculated from Equation (9) given by (Khurmi and Gupta, 2005).

$$T = \frac{p \times 60}{2\pi N} \quad (9)$$

Where,

- P = the calculated power (W)
 - N = the operating speed of the shaft (rpm)
 - T = Shaft torque
- Where P = 2 hp (1.491 kW) N = 1800 rpm
Shaft Torque is 44.4 Nm

2.4.5 Determination of Minimum Shaft Diameter.

The design for the Shaft of the Screw Conveyor (Auger) combined twisting moment and bending moment, so the shaft was designed based on two simultaneous moments on them.

$$d^3 = \frac{16T_s}{\sigma\pi} \quad (10)$$

- T_s = Shaft Torque
- σ = working stress

According to Khurmi and Gupta (2005), factor of safety for steel materials = 4, Maximum allowable working stress for shaft without keyway = 112 MN/m²

$$\text{factor of safety} = \frac{\text{allowable stress}}{\text{working stress}} \quad (11)$$

Working stress is 28MN/m²

Therefore,

$$d^3 = \frac{16 \times 44.4 \times 10^3}{28 \times 3.142}$$

$$d = \sqrt[3]{8152.8}$$

$$= 20.13 \text{ mm}$$

Figures 2, 3 and 4 show the Isometric view, Side view and Exploded view of the improved wet legume dehuller.

Figure 2. Isometric View of the Improved Wet legume Dehuller

Figure 3. Side view of the wet legume Dehuller

Figure 4. Exploded view of the wet Legume Dehuller

3. PERFORMANCE TEST

3.1 Test Procedure

The fabricated improved wet legume dehuller was subjected to a performance test. The machine was run at 320 rpm. Three different seeds (cowpea, locust beans and soybeans) were used to evaluate the performance of the machine on the basis of the dehulling efficiency, cleaning efficiency and percentage recovery.

The seeds (cowpea, locust beans and soybeans) were subjected to varying pretreatments before dehulling. Cowpea was soaked for 5 mins, 10 mins and 15 mins at room temperature, locust beans was cooked for 6 hrs, 9 hrs and 12 hrs while soya beans was soaked for 6 hrs, 12 hrs and 24 hrs at room temperature. The conditioned seeds were then weighed and fed into the dehulling chamber of the machine through the hopper.

During the test, data obtained include weight of sample fed into the hopper, retention time, weight of the sample from the cotyledon outlet and dehulling time were obtained and these were used to calculate and determine the values of the machine parameters. After the dehulling operation, sorting was carried out to determine the weights of unde-hulled seeds

Figure 5. Pictorial view of the Improved wet legume dehuller

3.2 Test Parameters

Equations (12) and (13) as described by the Standard test code for groundnut sheller, (NIS, 1997) were used to determine the dehulling efficiency and cleaning efficiency of the wet legume dehuller.

I. Dehulling Efficiency; DE (%): It is the weight of the cotyledon obtained at the cotyledon outlet over total weight of the both cotyledon and unde-hulled seed obtained at the cotyledon outlet in percentage. It is expressed as in Equation (12).

$$DE = \frac{W_1}{w_1 + w_2} \times 100\% \quad (12)$$

Where;

W_1 = weight of dehulled seeds (kg)

W_2 = Weight of un-dehulled seeds (kg)

II. Cleaning Efficiency; CE (%): It is the weight of the hull removed from cotyledon at the cotyledon outlet. Or weight of hull obtained at the cotyledon outlet over the expected weight of the hull from a given sample of dehulled conditioned leguminous seed in percentage subtracted from 100 as expressed in Equation (13).

$$CE = 100 - \left[\frac{W_4}{W_6} \times 100 \right] \% \quad (13)$$

W_4 as defined above

W_6 = Expected weight of the hull from a given sample of dehulled conditioned leguminous seed at both cotyledon outlet and hull outlet, (kg)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the summary of the values of the machine parameters obtained during the testing of the improved wet legume dehuller.

Table 1. Summary of Machine Parameters Values

S/N	Crop	Seed condition	Moisture content (% db)	Dehulling efficiency (%)	Cleaning efficiency (%)
1	Cowpea	5 mins	23.52±	38.35±	53.57±
		10 mins	32.84±	49.01±	71.58±
		15 mins	47.35±	55.81±	77.06±
2	Locust beans	6 hrs	103.82±	59.28±	73.71±
		9 hrs	79.63±	68.83±	81.00±
		12 hrs	55.82±	80.59±	92.53±
3	Soya beans	6 hrs	23.44±	56.02±	67.32±
		12 hrs	24.55±	62.41±	73.55±
		24 hrs	32.76±	75.02±	80.08±

4.1 Effect of seed conditioning on Moisture Content

From Table 1, it can be observed that moisture content is directly proportional to the soaking time for cowpea and soya beans. However, moisture content reduced with increased cooking time for locust beans after the sixth hour. This decrease in moisture content as cooking time increased is consistent with the findings of Audu and Umar (2004) who reported that, maximum moisture content is obtained at the sixth hour of cooking for locust beans.

4.2 Effect of Moisture Content on Dehulling Efficiency

For cowpea and soyabeans, a direct relationship was observed between moisture content and dehulling efficiency. As the moisture content of both seeds increased, dehulling efficiency also increased. This corroborated the findings of (Fathollahzadeh and Rajabipour, 2008), who reported that the forces required to cause rupture of the seed coat decreased with increased moisture content. In the case of locust beans, dehulling efficiency increased with a fall in moisture content and increased cooking time. This observation is in agreement with the findings of Faleye et al. (2013) and Gbabo et al. (2013) where it was reported that increased boiling time softened the seed coat and enhanced dehulling efficiency with minimal breakage, as elasticity increases with increased boiling time.

4.3 Effect of Moisture Content on Cleaning Efficiency

Efficiency of the dehulling operation is directly related to the cleaning efficiency of the wet legume dehuller. For cowpea and soyabeans, cleaning efficiency was observed to increase as the moisture content increased. It can be said that increase in moisture content enhances seed coat removal which has a direct relationship on the cleaning efficiency for cowpea and soyabeans.

However, increased cooking time, as reported by Faleye et al. (2013) and Gbabo et al. (2013), softened the seed coat which aids the seed coat removal which has a direct influence on the cleaning efficiency.

5. CONCLUSION

An improved wet legume dehuller was designed, constructed and tested. The following conclusions were obtained after testing the machine:

- a) The dehulling efficiency and cleaning efficiency of the machine increases as the moisture content of soyabeans and cowpea increases.
- b) The dehulling efficiency and cleaning efficiency of the machine increases as the cooking time of locust beans increases.

This confirms the fact that the dehulling and cleaning of seeds can be mechanized for agro-processors.

6. RECOMMENDATION

Extensive performance evaluation of the improved wet legume dehuller is recommended to determine the influence of different seed pretreatments and operating speeds on the performance of the machine.

Also, constant availability of sufficient water in the dehulling chamber will enhance the cleaning efficiency of the machine. It is therefore recommended that, the dehulling chamber be modified in such a way that sufficient water can be delivered directly into the dehulling chamber with the construction of water inlets that can be fitted with water delivery hoses.

REFERENCES

- Adejuyigbe S. B. and Bolaji B. O. (2005). Development and Performance Evaluation of Bean Dehuller. *Journal of Science and Technology*, 25(1):125 - 132.
- Aduba, J. J, Olotu, F. B. and Olaoye, J. O. (2013). Effects of Operative Processing Conditions on the Performance of Cowpea Dehuller Using Selected Cowpea Varieties, *International Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 2(3):71 - 78.
- Audu, A. and Umar, B. (2004). Development of a Concentric Cylinder Locust Bean Dehuller. *Agricultural Engineering International: the CIGR Journal of Scientific Research and Development*. Manuscript PM 04 003. Vol. VI.
- Babatunde O. O. (1995). "Development and Performance Evaluation of a Manually Operated Cowpea Dehulling Machine for Soaked Cowpea". *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Technology Vol.3*, Pp. 1-7.
- Egbe, E. A. P. and Roland B. O. (2016). "Design, Fabrication and Testing of a Wet Legume Dehulling Machine." *American Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, 4(3):108 - 111. doi: 10.12691/ajme-4-3-4.
- Faley T., Atere O., Oladipo O. and Agaju M. (2013). Determination of some of physical and mechanical properties of some cowpea varieties. *African J. Agriculture Research*, 8, 6485-6487.
- Fathollahzadeh H and Rajabipour A. 2008. Some mechanical properties of barberry. *International Agrophysics*, Vol. 22:299 – 302.
- Gbabo, A., Liberty J. T. and Fadele, O. S. (2013). Design, Construction and Assessment of African Locust Bean (*Parkia biglobosa*) Dehuller and Separator. *International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology (IJEIT)*, 3(5):438-444.
- Khurmi, R. and Gupta, J. K. (2005). *Textbook of Machine Design (S.I. Units) 4th Edition*. New Delhi: Eurasia Publishing House (PVT) LTD. Ram Nagar. Pp. 509 - 557.
- Ndukwu, M. C. and Onyenwoke, C. O. (2014), Development of Continuous Maize Dehulling, Cleaning and Milling Machine. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering and Technology*, 22(3):35 – 46.
- Nigerian Industrial Standard, Nigeria. (1997). *Standard Test Code for Groundnut Shellers, NIS 321*, Lagos: SON, Ikoyi, Lagos.
- Ogunsola, F. O., Ogundare, S. O., Jimo K. A and Oyeniyi, A. O. (2015). Development of a Motorized Wet Soybean De-Hulling Machine. *Journal for Studies in Management and Planning*. Volume 1, Issue 8; e-ISSN: 2395 – 0463. Pp 208 – 216. <http://internationaljournalofresearch.org/index.php/JSMaP>
- Okunola, A. A., T. A. Adekanye, A. Ayooluwa, C. E. Okonkwo, S. A. Alake, T. M. A. Olayanju, A. D. Adewumi (2019). Development of a Locust Bean Seed Dehulling Cum Washing Machine, *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 10(1):1321-1330.
- Olaoye, J. O and Olotu, F. B (2017). Development of a Hydro – Separating Cowpea Dehuller. *Agricultural Mechanization in Asia, African and Latin America*. Volume 48, No. 4, Autumn. Pg. 52 – 61. ISSN 0084 - 5841.
- Reichert, R. D., Lorser, E. C. and Young, C. G. (1979). *Village Scale Mechanical Dehulling of Cowpea*, *Cereal Chem.* 56, 181 - 184.